

Acupuncture and Evidence-Based Traditional Chinese Medicine Approaches for Mental Health.

Alexandre Penelas Constantino^{1*}, Tânia Martins Ferreira² .

¹ Independent researcher;

² ABS – Health Level, Atlântico Business School, Vila Nova de Gaia, Porto, Portugal;

* Correspondence: afpconstantino@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: Mental health is a complex topic with physical, emotional, and social implications. Traditional Chinese Medicine is a therapeutic option for various pathologies, with relevant applications for public health.

Objective: To analyse the effectiveness of Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), with a focus on acupuncture, as a complementary therapy for mental health.

Methods: Review of the scientific literature on the application of Traditional Chinese Medicine, especially acupuncture, based on studies of systematic reviews with meta-analyses.

Results: Acupuncture has demonstrated effectiveness in the treatment of various mental health conditions, with significant improvements observed in symptoms of depression, schizophrenia, cognitive impairment and insomnia. The combination of acupuncture with conventional treatments potentiated the clinical results. The mechanisms of action of acupuncture involve the regulation of neurotransmitters, the modulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis and the promotion of neuroplasticity. Other Traditional Chinese Medicine techniques, such as Taichi Chuan, *Qigong* and herbal medicine, have also shown relevant benefits.

Conclusion: Traditional Chinese Medicine, with a focus on acupuncture, represents a promising complementary approach to mental health, offering personalized and effective treatments. Its integration into mental health care can enhance clinical outcomes. Ongoing research is essential to deepen knowledge and optimize the application of these techniques.

Citation: Constantino A.P., Ferreira T.M., Leitão E., Silva P., Vieira E. Acupuncture and Evidence-Based Traditional Chinese Medicine Approaches for Mental Health. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2025;3(3) 10.5281/zenodo.17257364

Academic Editor: Jorge Rodrigues

Received: 17 July 2025

Reviewed: 17 August 2025

Revised: 27 August 2025

Revised: 29 September 2025

Accepted: 1 October 2025

Published: 3 October 2025

Publisher's Note: IPTC stays neutral concerning jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Keywords: Mental health; Depression; Schizophrenia; Parkinson's Disease; Cognitive impairment; Insomnia; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Acupuncture.

1. Mental Health

Mental health is a broad domain encompassing cognitive, emotional, social, and behavioural functioning ¹. According to the DSM-5 (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, 5th edition), a mental disorder corresponds to a clinically significant alteration of cognitive processes, emotional regulation, or behaviour, reflecting psychological, biological, or developmental dysfunction ².

Mental health problems represent a significant burden at the individual, social, and economic levels. They are often associated with work incapacity ³, reflected both in loss of productivity and increased costs with medical care, therapies, and support services.

In addition, they manifest in physical consequences, such as sleep disturbances, chronic fatigue, and worsening of other health conditions. These repercussions also extend to families and support networks, who face considerable emotional and financial burdens, while the social stigma associated with mental disorders may exacerbate exclusion and discrimination ⁴.

Mental disorders are also among the main direct and indirect causes of hospitalization⁵⁻⁷, and according to Garcia-Ceja *et al.*⁴, the deficit in access to treatment remains a global problem, both in developed and developing countries. Contributing factors include the shortage of qualified professionals, the high cost of treatments, and the insufficiency of quality mental health services. In many cases, people with mental disorders end up seeking emergency services or being hospitalized due to acute crises or health complications.

Several factors influence mental health, interacting with one another and placing mental disorders on a spectrum that integrates both biological and psychosocial components⁸.

The relationship between mental health and physiological parameters has been documented: elevated inflammatory levels are associated with depressive symptoms, platelet distribution width may represent a risk marker, and the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio negatively correlates with psychological well-being⁹.

This interdependence helps explain the high comorbidity between mental disorders and cardiovascular, oncological, and metabolic diseases¹⁰⁻¹³.

Despite this complexity, risk factors for mental health can be grouped into three major categories: biological, psychological, and social¹⁴.

Among biological factors, physical health and clinical conditions stand out, often associated with anxiety, depression¹⁵⁻¹⁸, and increased risk of suicide¹⁹. Sleep disorders represent an additional physiological vulnerability^{20,21}, and genetic factors play a significant role in this domain^{22,23}.

Regarding psychological factors, several can be identified, namely personality traits, self-esteem, coping mechanisms, and life experiences^{14,24,25}. Patients with treatment-resistant depression tend to present personality traits of high harm avoidance and low reward-seeking, which may hinder recovery²⁶. Likewise, Orth *et al.*²⁷ indicate that low self-esteem is associated with an increased risk of depression throughout adulthood. Similarly, crises such as natural disasters and nuclear accidents have demonstrated a substantial impact on the psychological suffering of populations, likely intensified by the perception of risk²⁸.

As for social factors, these include social support, interpersonal relationships, work context, socioeconomic conditions, and culture^{24,29,30}. A longitudinal study with Latino youth in the USA showed that length of stay in the USA was associated with certain challenges and school engagement, while parental involvement in American culture appeared protective against social and behavioural problems. Interestingly, adolescents' involvement with their culture of origin proved beneficial for self-esteem and was associated with less hopelessness and aggression over time³¹.

Romito *et al.*³² also indicate that past and present experiences of physical violence or relational abuse are strongly related to worse mental health outcomes.

In this scenario, the exploration of complementary interventions has gained relevance, offering new perspectives for mental health promotion. Among these, TCM, particularly acupuncture, stands out, whose integration with conventional treatments may contribute to more holistic, personalized, and potentially effective approaches.

1.1. Most Common Mental Disorders

Mental health, understood as a state of well-being in which the individual recognizes and develops their abilities, copes with daily stress, works productively, and contributes to their community, is fundamental for individual and social functioning³³. However, mental disorders, characterized by alterations in thinking, mood, and/or behaviour, are prevalent and have a substantial personal, familial, and social impact.

Depression

It is one of the most frequent disorders, characterized by persistently depressed mood, anhedonia, changes in sleep and appetite, fatigue, feelings of guilt or worthlessness, concentration deficits, and, in severe cases, suicidal ideation³⁴. Epidemiological studies demonstrate high lifetime prevalence^{35,36}. Its impact is vast, reflected in reduced quality of life, increased risk of physical comorbidities, and premature mortality. It compromises the ability to maintain healthy interpersonal relationships, affecting family life, friendships, and marital stability. It is also associated with work absenteeism, reduced productivity, and increased healthcare costs^{37,38}.

Anxiety Disorders

The prevalence of anxiety disorders are high³⁹⁻⁴¹, with repercussions on interpersonal relationships, academic and work performance, and an increased risk of other mental and physical disorders⁴². They include generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, specific phobias, social anxiety disorder, and post-traumatic stress disorder^{43,44}.

- Generalized anxiety disorder is characterized by excessive and persistent worry about various aspects of life;
- Panic disorder involves sudden attacks of intense fear accompanied by physical symptoms;
- Specific phobias are irrational fears of particular objects or situations;
- Social anxiety disorder involves fear of social or performance situations;
- Post-traumatic stress disorder occurs after traumatic events, manifesting as flashbacks, hypervigilance, avoidance, and negative mood and cognitive changes³⁴.

Bipolar Disorder

This condition involves alternating episodes of mania/hypomania and depressive episodes, characterized by extreme fluctuations in mood, energy, cognition, and behaviour³⁴. Its prevalence is significant⁴⁵, with important consequences: occupational and social dysfunction, high suicide risk, and comorbidities with other mental and physical disorders⁴⁶.

Schizophrenia

It is a chronic mental disorder that affects thinking, emotions, and behaviour. It manifests through positive symptoms (delusions, hallucinations, disorganized speech), negative symptoms (lack of affect, motivation deficits, poverty of speech), and cognitive symptoms (memory and attention deficits)³⁴. The prevalence is around 1% of the global population, typically appearing in late adolescence or early adulthood⁴⁷. The impact is severe, compromising social and occupational functioning and significantly increasing suicide risk⁴⁸. Its treatment is multimodal, combining pharmacotherapy (antipsychotics) and psychosocial interventions (cognitive-behavioural therapy, social rehabilitation), with early intervention being crucial for prognosis⁴⁹⁻⁵².

Parkinson's Disease

Although it is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder caused by the loss of dopamine-producing neurons in the brain, primarily affecting movement through resting tremor, muscle rigidity, bradykinesia (slowness of movement), and postural instability^{53,54}, it has a strong impact on mental health. In addition to motor symptoms, depression, anxiety, loss of smell, cognitive deficits, and sleep disturbances are common⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷. Its prevalence increases with age, leading to growing disability and dependence, affecting about 1% of individuals over 60 years⁵⁸. Treatment primarily aims to control symptoms through

medication that increases dopamine levels (such as levodopa) and other pharmacological therapies⁵⁹. Physiotherapy, occupational therapy, and speech therapy are also essential to maintain mobility and function⁶⁰.

It should be noted that these disorders often coexist, complicating diagnosis and treatment and exacerbating clinical and social impact⁶¹. Risk factors such as family history, traumatic experiences, substance use, and chronic diseases contribute to increased vulnerability³³.

2. Traditional Chinese Medicine

TCM is a holistic healthcare system with more than 2,500 years of history in ancient China⁶²⁻⁶⁴. It is deeply rooted in the belief that the human body is an interconnected system of physical, emotional, and spiritual aspects, whose balance is essential for maintaining health⁶⁵. In contrast to Western medicine, often oriented toward treating specific diseases or symptoms, TCM seeks to maintain and restore overall harmony in the body through natural methods, including both preventive strategies and therapeutic interventions, always individualized according to the patient's needs⁶⁶⁻⁷⁰.

Its origins trace back to ancient China, where early medical knowledge was orally transmitted by shamans, herbalists, and healers. These teachings were shaped by philosophical traditions such as Taoism, Confucianism, and Buddhism, emphasizing harmony, balance, and interdependence among all things^{71,72}. Early written records date from the *Shang* Dynasty (1600–1046 BCE), but it was primarily during the *Han* Dynasty (206 BCE–220 CE) that TCM's theoretical foundations were consolidated⁷².

Among the most influential classical works, the *Huangdi Neijing* (The Inner Canon of the Yellow Emperor), written around the 3rd century BCE and attributed to the legendary Yellow Emperor, *Huangdi*, is considered the foundation of TCM theory. It addresses the principles of *Qi*, *Yin-Yang*, the Five Elements, and the relationship between the human body and the natural world, forming TCM's conceptual core^{73,74}. The *Shennong Bencaojing* (Divine Farmer's *Materia Medica*) of the 1st century CE is another foundational work, cataloguing over 365 substances of plant, mineral, and animal origin, serving as a guide for herbal medicine practice to this day⁷⁵.

With the development of Chinese civilization, TCM evolved alongside other scientific and philosophical advancements. During the *Tang* and *Song* Dynasties (618–1279 CE), it flourished and became more systematized, expanding its influence to neighbouring regions such as Korea, Japan, and Vietnam⁷⁶⁻⁷⁹. During the *Qing* Dynasty (1644–1912 CE), it reached a high degree of consolidation, with well-established schools of thought and a wide network of practitioners throughout China. These legacies continue to underpin contemporary TCM practice, maintaining its relevance both in traditional contexts and in dialogue with modern medicine.

2.1. Traditional Concepts in Chinese Medicine

The concept of *Qi* holds a central position in TCM. It refers to the vital force or energy that flows through all living beings. From the TCM perspective, health results from the harmonious and continuous flow of *Qi* along the meridians (energy channels), while disease arises when this flow is blocked, deficient, or excessive. The goal is to maintain or restore balanced *Qi* circulation, ensuring proper body and mind function. Importantly, *Qi* is not only defined as physical energy but also as a force influencing mental, emotional, and spiritual levels, directly affecting emotions and consciousness^{80,81}.

Another fundamental principle is the *Yin-Yang* theory, describing the dynamic polarity present in all natural and bodily phenomena. Yin and Yang are opposite but complementary and interdependent forces, constantly transforming. *Yin* represents passive aspects (cold, dark, nourishing), whereas *Yang* corresponds to active qualities (warm,

bright, stimulating). Health is understood as the dynamic balance between *Yin* and *Yang*. Relative *Yang* predominance may manifest as fever, inflammation, or mental agitation, while relative *Yin* excess may result in fatigue, feeling cold, or lethargy^{65,81}.

The Five Elements theory (Wood, Fire, Earth, Metal, and Water) complements these principles, explaining interactions between different aspects of the human body and the natural environment. Each element is associated with a specific organ, season, emotion, colour, and sound, forming a system of correspondences guiding both diagnosis and clinical treatment. For example, Wood corresponds to the Liver and is linked to anger, while Fire is associated with the Heart and relates to joy. Figure 1 illustrates how the Five Elements relate to the physiological and emotional dimensions of the body, organized into two essential cycles: generation and control. In the generation cycle, each element nourishes or promotes the next: Wood feeds Fire, Fire generates Earth, Earth produces Metal, Metal condenses and collects Water, and Water nourishes Wood. In the control cycle, each element keeps another in check, preventing excess: Wood controls Earth, Earth contains Water, Water dominates Fire, Fire melts Metal, and Metal cuts Wood.

Figure 1. The Five Elements theory: Organs, Seasons, Emotion, and Sounds.

Fundamentally, TCM seeks to maintain a state of dynamic balance between the internal and external environment. The concept of balance permeates all aspects of TCM, from *Qi* flow to the regulation of bodily fluids, emotions, and the balance of heat and cold. The body is viewed as a constantly adapting system seeking homeostasis and integration with its surroundings.

2.2. Traditional Chinese Medicine and Mental Health

TCM is a holistic medicine that considers health as the cooperative functioning of various biological systems, which may interact negatively when disturbed. Mental health has emerged as a global priority in recent decades, leading to interest in complementary and integrative therapeutic approaches. TCM, with its holistic vision of the human being, understands health as a harmonious and cooperative state among different biological systems, which can interact negatively when there is imbalance or dysfunction⁸².

In the West, researchers have sought to interpret TCM's philosophical and theoretical foundations and relate them to modern biomedical language^{65,83-86}. With scientific advances supporting the efficacy of some TCM techniques, its role in integrative medicine is increasingly recognized, considered a promising complement to conventional Western medicine⁸⁷⁻⁹³.

Specifically regarding mental health, TCM has been observed to play a complementary and beneficial role, helping to provide more accessible, cost-effective, and feasible mental healthcare^{85,94-98}.

Several core concepts and principles of TCM are important to understand regarding this topic.

Shen

In TCM, the concept of *Shen* plays a crucial role, representing the mental, emotional, and spiritual dimension of the human being. *Shen* is considered the subtlest manifestation of life, reflecting consciousness, emotions, and spirit⁹⁹. It is described as the "spiritual essence" that resides in the body and coordinates mental, cognitive, and emotional faculties. Together with *Jing*, the vital essence, and *Qi*, the vital energy, it constitutes the so-called Three Treasures (*San Bao*), which sustain human existence in all dimensions¹⁰⁰.

Shen is closely associated with the Heart, considered its residence in TCM. The *Huangdi Neijing* states that "the Heart is the sovereign of the organs and houses the *Shen*", emphasizing the Heart's central role in governing the mind and emotions. Thus, the harmonious circulation of *Qi* and *Xue* of the Heart is essential to nourish *Shen* and ensure mental clarity and emotional stability^{100,101}. Balanced *Shen* manifests as a clear, calm, and focused mind, restful sleep, appropriate emotional expression, bright eyes, and coherent communication. Conversely, when *Shen* is disturbed, signs such as anxiety, insomnia, excessive dreaming, palpitations, memory loss, depression, agitation, or even manic states may appear, depending on the severity of the imbalance⁴⁹⁻⁵². Understanding and nurturing *Shen* is therefore essential for preventing mental disorders and promoting a balanced and fulfilling life⁹⁹.

Mental Processes in Traditional Chinese Medicine

In TCM, mental and emotional processes are intrinsically linked to physiological functions. Excessive or poorly regulated emotions can affect the balance of *Qi*, *Xue* (blood), and internal organs, leading to disharmonies reflected in both body and mind⁸⁴.

According to the Five Elements theory, each *Zang-Fu* organ is associated with a specific emotion or mental process, so psychological and spiritual health depends directly on the harmony among these systems. When an organ is balanced, the corresponding emotion manifests healthily; in imbalance, physical and psychological symptoms emerge. Table 1 presents these associations between elements, organs, and mental processes according to classical TCM.

Thus, the importance of emotions in physiological systems is clear. In TCM's bidirectional view, mental and physiological processes mutually influence each other, not as isolated entities but as expressions of internal organ activity. Each emotion is linked not only to an organ but also to its energetic function. Anger, for example, relates to the Liver and may manifest as *Qi* stagnation, headaches, muscle tension, or menstrual disturbances. Emotions are not inherently negative unless excessive or disharmonious. Joy, for instance,

is positive but when excessive may “agitate the Heart,” causing insomnia and mental agitation. Repetitive thinking, linked to the Spleen-Pancreas, impairs digestion and mental clarity, while prolonged sadness weakens the Lung, predisposing to isolation and physical vulnerability.

Table 1. Associations between Elements, Organs, and Their Emotions according to Traditional Chinese Medicine.

Element	Organs (<i>Zang-Fu</i>)	Emotions and Mental Processes	
		Excess	Deficiency
Wood	Liver - Gallbladder	Excessive anger, irritability, frustration	Shyness, indecision, lack of motivation
Fire	Heart - Small Intestine	Joy/euphoria, insomnia, agitation	Apathy, depression, lack of vitality
Earth	Spleen-Pancreas - Stomach	Rumination, obsessiveness	Mental fatigue, concentration difficulties
Metal	Lung - Large Intestine	Sadness, melancholy, excessive attachment, excessive worry	Inability to feel sadness or process loss, emotional detachment
Water	Kidney - Bladder	Intense fear, panic, shock	Recklessness, loss of willpower

In diagnosis, the practitioner observes not only physical signs but also emotional aspects, such as eye brightness, facial colour, and tone of voice. Conversely, physiological imbalances can generate emotional states. For example, Kidney imbalance may cause fear or insecurity, and prolonged Lung deficiency may increase vulnerability to sadness or social withdrawal.

This integrated view expands therapeutic possibilities, allowing treatment of emotional imbalances by harmonizing the corresponding organs through acupuncture, herbal therapy, *Qigong*, or dietotherapy, highlighting TCM’s preventive and therapeutic value in promoting mental and emotional health.

2.3. Acupuncture for Mental Health

Acupuncture consists of the insertion of fine needles at specific points along the meridians, aiming to regulate the flow of *Qi* and promote the body’s homeostasis^{82,102}. The selection of points is individualized, considering the patient’s symptoms and energetic diagnosis. Studies show that acupuncture can be effective in treating chronic pain, stress, and conditions such as migraines, insomnia, and nausea, suggesting mechanisms of action related to neurotransmitter modulation and autonomic nervous system activity¹⁰³⁻¹¹⁰.

A recent systematic review⁸² concluded that TCM techniques, including acupuncture, may be useful in treating mental disorders and improving quality of life in patients with physical conditions associated with psychological distress. The following sections present scientific studies using acupuncture specifically in various areas of mental health.

Depression

Analyzing seven clinical trials, Wang *et al.*¹¹¹ suggest that acupuncture can significantly reduce the severity of major depression and depressive neurosis compared to placebo control.

More recently, Smith *et al.*¹¹² analysed 64 clinical trials using acupuncture as an intervention for depression. They concluded that acupuncture may have positive effects on

depression, emphasizing the benefits of combining acupuncture with medication. In the 12 studies comparing acupuncture plus medication with medication alone, the combined approach was statistically superior. When compared with psychological therapy, acupuncture tended to produce more positive outcomes with fewer side effects.

These meta-analytic studies suggest that acupuncture can be a valuable tool in treating depression, especially when used alongside conventional medication.

Schizophrenia

Shen *et al.*¹¹³ analyzed the use of acupuncture in combination with conventional antipsychotic treatment in schizophrenia. Among the 30 studies included, they observed that adding acupuncture to standard-dose antipsychotics led to short- and medium-term improvements in psychiatric symptom severity compared to medication alone. Short-term improvements in psychotic symptoms were also noted. For negative symptom severity, acupuncture showed value as an adjunct to conventional medication in both short- and medium-term follow-up. Relapse rates were also reduced when acupuncture was used alongside a low dose of antipsychotics compared to a standard dose, with the additional benefit of reducing medication-related side effects. These findings suggest that acupuncture may have therapeutic value in schizophrenia, particularly as a complement to antipsychotic medication.

Parkinson's Disease and Cognitive Deficit

Liu *et al.*¹¹⁴ analyzed 11 clinical trials regarding acupuncture's effect on Parkinson's disease. They concluded that acupuncture combined with the conventional drug Madopar improved clinical efficacy compared to the drug alone. Additionally, the combination produced significantly fewer adverse effects, including gastrointestinal reactions, "on-off" phenomena, and mental disturbances.

Regarding cognitive improvement, Kim *et al.*¹¹⁵ analysed acupuncture's potential compared to conventional medication. Results suggested that acupuncture could effectively enhance cognitive function in patients with mild cognitive impairment.

These findings indicate that acupuncture may be a useful complementary therapy in Parkinson's disease, potentially providing advantages in cases of cognitive decline.

Insomnia

Kim *et al.*¹¹⁶ analysed 19 clinical trials, suggesting that in a personalized approach according to TCM principles, acupuncture may be more effective than medication for insomnia, both in response rates and sleep quality.

2.4. Mechanisms of Acupuncture in Mental Health

In general, acupuncture aims to regulate the nervous, circulatory, endocrine, and exocrine systems and promote well-being¹⁰². Regarding its specific action in mental disorders, various mechanisms are proposed in the scientific literature. Yang *et al.*¹¹⁷ state that acupuncture may alleviate depression by promoting hippocampal neuroplasticity, enhancing neural network function, and reducing brain inflammation. By regulating neurotransmitter levels and modulating the neuroendocrine axis, acupuncture contributes to improved emotional state and exhibits an antidepressant effect¹¹⁸. Tu *et al.*¹¹⁹, suggest that acupuncture can modulate glutamate receptors and excitatory amino acid transporters, potentially serving as complementary therapy for certain neuropsychiatric disorders. In addition, Zhao *et al.*¹²⁰ propose that acupuncture can protect dopaminergic neurons from degeneration via antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-apoptotic pathways, and modulate neurotransmitter balance in the basal ganglia circuits. As well, acupuncture has been shown to regulate hormonal levels associated with the HPA axis^{121,122}, which has implications for treating anxiety, depression, stress management, and sleep disorders.

2.5. Other TCM Techniques for Mental Health

TCM integrates various therapeutic practices beyond acupuncture, many of which are relevant to mental health.

Taichi Chuan and Qigong

These are ancient practices involving slow, deliberate movements combined with controlled breathing and meditation to cultivate and balance *Qi* ^{123,124}. They are believed to improve health by harmonizing internal energy, reducing stress, and increasing physical flexibility and strength. *Qigong* is often used as preventive medicine, while *Taichi* is practiced as a low-impact exercise ⁸⁵.

A meta-analysis ¹²⁵ suggests that *Taichi Chuan* significantly improves depressive symptoms. Similarly, *Qigong* showed superiority over active and passive controls in reducing depression ¹²⁶.

For anxiety, both practices appear to provide symptomatic improvement ^{125,127}. Regarding mild cognitive impairment, Lin *et al.* ¹²⁸ reported gains in global function, memory, learning, visuospatial ability, and executive function. Yang *et al.* ¹²⁹ also reported benefits in attention, abstraction, and mental flexibility. Additionally, Wu *et al.* ¹³⁰ demonstrated positive effects on sleep quality.

Chinese Herbal Medicine

This is a major branch of TCM, using plants, minerals, and animal products to restore health ^{131,132}. Over 500 substances are frequently used, generally combined in balanced formulas targeting both the underlying cause and symptoms. These may be administered as decoctions, powders, capsules, or topical preparations. Well-known herbs include Ginseng, Licorice, *Angelica Sinensis* (*Dong Quai*), and Reishi mushroom ¹³³⁻¹³⁶.

Despite being an ancient practice, herbal medicine continues to be widely applied and studied across multiple clinical areas ^{131,132,137-141}, including mental health ^{139,142,143}.

Table 2 summarizes various herbal applications for mental health.

Table 2. Classic Chinese Herbal Formulas Applied to Mental Health Disorders.

Pathology		Actions	Evidence
Depression	<i>Chai Hu Shu Gan San</i>	Harmonizes Liver <i>Qi</i> , relieves stagnation, regulates emotions	Sun <i>et al.</i> ¹⁴⁴ : superior efficacy to fluoxetine
	<i>Bupleurum</i>	Frees Liver, regulates <i>Qi</i> , stabilizes emotions	Yang <i>et al.</i> ¹⁴⁵ : superior to selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors
Schizophrenia	<i>Wendan Tang</i>	Resolves phlegm-heat, harmonizes Stomach and Gallbladder, calms <i>Shen</i>	Deng <i>et al.</i> ¹⁴⁶ : enhances antipsychotic effects, reduces adverse effects
Insomnia	<i>Long Dan Xie Gan Tang</i>	Drains Liver Fire, calms <i>Shen</i> , improves sleep	Fan <i>et al.</i> ¹⁴⁷ : slightly superior to conventional medication, with fewer side effects
	<i>Shumian</i>	Nourishes Heart and Spleen, calms <i>Shen</i> , regulates sleep	Wang <i>et al.</i> ¹⁴⁸ : efficacy equivalent to pharmacological medication

3. Final Considerations

Mental health is a complex topic with physical, emotional, and social implications. This work shows that TCM offers a holistic approach, considering health as a result of balance among biological systems, and may play a complementary role in mental health.

Specifically, acupuncture has shown efficacy in treating various mental health conditions, including depression, schizophrenia, Parkinson's disease, cognitive deficits, and insomnia. Scientific evidence indicates that, especially when combined with conventional treatments, acupuncture can significantly improve clinical outcomes. Mechanisms involve neurotransmitter regulation, HPA axis modulation, and neuroplasticity promotion.

Other techniques, such as *Taichi Chuan*, *Qigong*, and herbal medicine, also show proven benefits in scientific studies, reinforcing TCM's potential as a complementary therapy.

Integrating TCM into mental healthcare may provide more accessible, cost-effective, and personalized approaches, enhancing conventional therapies. However, it is essential that these techniques are applied by qualified professionals in compliance with current legislation.

Limitations include the need for ongoing research to deepen understanding of mechanisms, optimize therapeutic protocols, and systematically explore technique combinations.

4. Conclusions

This work highlights the potential of TCM, with a focus on acupuncture, as a complementary approach in mental health. TCM's holistic vision allows for personalized and effective treatments in conditions such as depression, schizophrenia, insomnia, and cognitive deficits. Scientific evidence supports acupuncture's efficacy, particularly when combined with conventional treatments, through neurotransmitter regulation and hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis modulation. Other techniques, such as *Taichi Chuan*, *Qigong*, and herbal medicine, also demonstrate significant clinical benefits.

These therapies should be applied only by qualified professionals. Continuous research is necessary to expand knowledge, optimize protocols, and consolidate the integration of TCM into mental healthcare.

Credit author statement: Conceptualisation, A.P.C.; Methodology, A.P.C.; Validation, T.M.F., E.L., P.S. and E.V.; Formal analysis, A.P.C.; Investigation, A.P.C. and T.M.F.; Resources T.M.F., E.L., P.S. and E.V.; Data Curation, A.P.C.; Writing - Original Draft, A.P.C.; Writing - Review & Editing, T.M.F., E.L., P.S. and E.V.; Visualisation, T.M.F.; Supervision, T.M.F.; Project administration A.P.C. and T.M.F. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

References

1. Bitsko RH, Claussen AH, Lichstein J, Black LI, Jones SE, Danielson ML, et al. Mental Health Surveillance Among Children - United States, 2013-2019. *MMWR Suppl.* 2022;71(2):1-42. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.su7102a1>
2. APA. Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders 2013. 591-643 p.

3. Kessler RC, Frank RG. The impact of psychiatric disorders on work loss days. *Psychol Med.* 1997;27(4):861-73. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0033291797004807>
4. Garcia-Ceja E, Riegler M, Nordgreen T, Jakobsen P, Oedegaard KJ, Tørresen J. Mental health monitoring with multimodal sensing and machine learning: A survey. *Pervasive and Mobile Computing.* 2018;51:1-26. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmcj.2018.09.003>
5. Marten Wd, Wilkerson B. Stress, work and mental health: a global perspective. *Acta neuropsychiatrica.* 2003;15(1):44-53. doi:
6. Bernardes C, Massano J, Freitas A. Hospital admissions 2000-2014: A retrospective analysis of 288 096 events in patients with dementia. *Arch Gerontol Geriatr.* 2018;77:150-7. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.archger.2018.05.006>
7. Lee S, Lee W, Kim D, Kim E, Myung W, Kim SY, et al. Short-term PM(2.5) exposure and emergency hospital admissions for mental disease. *Environ Res.* 2019;171:313-20. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.01.036>
8. Ahn WK, Proctor CC, Flanagan EH. Mental Health Clinicians' Beliefs About the Biological, Psychological, and Environmental Bases of Mental Disorders. *Cogn Sci.* 2009;33(2):147-82. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1551-6709.2009.01008.x>
9. Gialluisi A, Bonaccio M, Di Castelnuovo A, Costanzo S, De Curtis A, Sarchiapone M, et al. Lifestyle and biological factors influence the relationship between mental health and low-grade inflammation. *Brain Behav Immun.* 2020;85:4-13. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbi.2019.04.041>
10. Chaddha A, Robinson EA, Kline-Rogers E, Alexandris-Souphis T, Rubenfire M. Mental Health and Cardiovascular Disease. *Am J Med.* 2016;129(11):1145-8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjmed.2016.05.018>
11. Dhar AK, Barton DA. Depression and the Link with Cardiovascular Disease. *Front Psychiatry.* 2016;7:33. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2016.00033>
12. Young K, Singh G. Biological Mechanisms of Cancer-Induced Depression. *Front Psychiatry.* 2018;9:299. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2018.00299>
13. Darwish L, Beroncal E, Sison MV, Swardfager W. Depression in people with type 2 diabetes: current perspectives. *Diabetes, metabolic syndrome and obesity : targets and therapy.* 2018;11:333-43. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2147/DMSO.S106797>
14. Sheldon E, Simmonds-Buckley M, Bone C, Mascarenhas T, Chan N, Wincott M, et al. Prevalence and risk factors for mental health problems in university undergraduate students: A systematic review with meta-analysis. *J Affect Disord.* 2021;287:282-92. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2021.03.054>
15. Andrews B, Wilding JM. The relation of depression and anxiety to life-stress and achievement in students. *Br J Psychol.* 2004;95(Pt 4):509-21. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1348/0007126042369802>
16. Jessop DC, Reid M, Solomon L. Financial concern predicts deteriorations in mental and physical health among university students. *Psychology & health.* 2020;35(2):196-209.
17. Silva V, Costa P, Pereira I, Faria R, Salgueira AP, Costa MJ, et al. Depression in medical students: insights from a longitudinal study. *BMC Med Educ.* 2017;17(1):184. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-017-1006-0>
18. Richardson T, Elliott P, Roberts R. Relationship between loneliness and mental health in students. *Journal of public mental health.* 2017;16(2):48-54.
19. Blasco MJ, Vilagut G, Alayo I, Almenara J, Cebria AI, Echeburua E, et al. First-onset and persistence of suicidal ideation in university students: A one-year follow-up study. *J Affect Disord.* 2019;256:192-204. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2019.05.035>
20. Hossain S, Anjum A, Uddin ME, Rahman MA, Hossain MF. Impacts of socio-cultural environment and lifestyle factors on the psychological health of university students in Bangladesh: A longitudinal study. *J Affect Disord.* 2019;256:393-403. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2019.06.001>
21. Semplonius T, Willoughby T. A person-centered analysis of sleep and emotion dysregulation: Short- and long-term links with depression and alcohol use. *J Am Coll Health.* 2019;67(5):486-96. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07448481.2018.1497637>
22. De Geus E, De Moor M. A genetic perspective on the association between exercise and mental health. *Mental health and physical activity.* 2008;1(2):53-61.

23. de Geus EJ. A genetic perspective on the association between exercise and mental health in the era of genome-wide association studies. *Mental health and physical activity*. 2021;20:100378.
24. Mechanic D. Sociocultural and socio-psychological factors affecting personal responses to psychological disorder. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*. 1975;16(4):393-404.
25. Kovacs M, Goldston D, Obrosky DS, Bonar LK. Psychiatric disorders in youths with IDDM: rates and risk factors. *Diabetes Care*. 1997;20(1):36-44. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2337/diacare.20.1.36>
26. Takahashi M, Shirayama Y, Muneoka K, Suzuki M, Sato K, Hashimoto K. Personality traits as risk factors for treatment-resistant depression. *PloS one*. 2013;8(5):e63756. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0063756>
27. Orth U, Robins RW, Trzesniewski KH, Maes J, Schmitt M. Low self-esteem is a risk factor for depressive symptoms from young adulthood to old age. *Journal of abnormal psychology*. 2009;118(3):472.
28. Kunii Y, Suzuki Y, Shiga T, Yabe H, Yasumura S, Maeda M, et al. Severe Psychological Distress of Evacuees in Evacuation Zone Caused by the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant Accident: The Fukushima Health Management Survey. *PloS one*. 2016;11(7):e0158821. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0158821>
29. Pinto AC, Luna IT, Sivla Ade A, Pinheiro PN, Braga VA, Souza AM. [Risk factors associated with mental health issues in adolescents: a integrative review]. *Revista da Escola de Enfermagem da U S P*. 2014;48(3):555-64. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1590/s0080-623420140000300022>
30. Davis E, Sawyer MG, Lo SK, Priest N, Wake M. Socioeconomic risk factors for mental health problems in 4–5-year-old children: Australian population study. *Academic Pediatrics*. 2010;10(1):41-7.
31. Smokowski P, Buchanan RL, Bacallao ML. Acculturation and adjustment in Latino adolescents: how cultural risk factors and assets influence multiple domains of adolescent mental health. *J Prim Prev*. 2009;30(3-4):371-93. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10935-009-0179-7>
32. Romito P, Molzan Turan J, De Marchi M. The impact of current and past interpersonal violence on women's mental health. *Soc Sci Med*. 2005;60(8):1717-27. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2004.08.026>
33. World Health Organization. *The World Health Report 2001: Mental health: new understanding, new hope*. 2001.
34. American Psychiatric Association. *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5®)*: American Psychiatric Publishing; 2013. 9780890425572.
35. Goodwin RD, Dierker LC, Wu M, Galea S, Hoven CW, Weinberger AH. Trends in US depression prevalence from 2015 to 2020: the widening treatment gap. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*. 2022;63(5):726-33.
36. Weinberger AH, Gbedemah M, Martinez AM, Nash D, Galea S, Goodwin RD. Trends in depression prevalence in the USA from 2005 to 2015: widening disparities in vulnerable groups. *Psychol Med*. 2018;48(8):1308-15. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291717002781>
37. Liu Q, He H, Yang J, Feng X, Zhao F, Lyu J. Changes in the global burden of depression from 1990 to 2017: Findings from the Global Burden of Disease study. *J Psychiatr Res*. 2020;126:134-40. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2019.08.002>
38. Hoppen TH, Priebe S, Vetter I, Morina N. Global burden of post-traumatic stress disorder and major depression in countries affected by war between 1989 and 2019: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ global health*. 2021;6(7):e006303.
39. Kan FP, Raoofi S, Rafiei S, Khani S, Hosseinifard H, Tajik F, et al. A systematic review of the prevalence of anxiety among the general population during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of affective disorders*. 2021;293:391-8.
40. Matsuyama S, Otsubo T, Nomoto K, Higa S, Takashio O. Prevalence of Generalized Anxiety Disorder in Japan: A General Population Survey. *Neuropsychiatr Dis Treat*. 2024;20:1355-66. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2147/NDT.S456272>
41. Hajek A, Konig HH. Prevalence and Correlates of Individuals Screening Positive for Depression and Anxiety on the PHQ-4 in the German General Population: Findings from the Nationally Representative German Socio-Economic Panel (GSOEP). *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020;17(21):7865. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17217865>
42. Craske MG, Stein MB. Anxiety. *Lancet*. 2016;388(10063):3048-59. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(16\)30381-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(16)30381-6)

43. Himanshu, Dharmila, Sarkar D, Nutan. A Review of Behavioral Tests to Evaluate Different Types of Anxiety and Anti-anxiety Effects. *Clin Psychopharmacol Neurosci*. 2020;18(3):341-51. doi: <https://doi.org/10.9758/cpn.2020.18.3.341>
44. Nowak J, Nikendei C, Rollmann I, Orth M, Friederich H-C, Kindermann D. Characterization of different types of anxiety disorders in relation to structural integration of personality and adverse and protective childhood experiences in psychotherapy outpatients—a cross-sectional study. *BMC psychiatry*. 2023;23(1):501.
45. Merikangas KR, Akiskal HS, Angst J, Greenberg PE, Hirschfeld RM, Petukhova M, et al. Lifetime and 12-month prevalence of bipolar spectrum disorder in the National Comorbidity Survey replication. *Arch Gen Psychiatry*. 2007;64(5):543-52. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1001/archpsyc.64.5.543>
46. Grande I, Berk M, Birmaher B, Vieta E. Bipolar disorder. *Lancet*. 2016;387(10027):1561-72. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(15\)00241-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(15)00241-X)
47. McGrath J, Saha S, Chant D, Welham J. Schizophrenia: a concise overview of incidence, prevalence, and mortality. *Epidemiol Rev*. 2008;30(1):67-76. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/epirev/mxn001>
48. Caldwell CB, Gottesman, II. Schizophrenics kill themselves too: a review of risk factors for suicide. *Schizophr Bull*. 1990;16(4):571-89. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/schbul/16.4.571>
49. Hill SK, Bishop JR, Palumbo D, Sweeney JA. Effect of second-generation antipsychotics on cognition: current issues and future challenges. *Expert Rev Neurother*. 2010;10(1):43-57. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1586/ern.09.143>
50. Jauhar S, Laws KR, McKenna PJ. CBT for schizophrenia: a critical viewpoint. *Psychol Med*. 2019;49(8):1233-6. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291718004166>
51. Turkington D, Dudley R, Warman DM, Beck AT. Cognitive-behavioral therapy for schizophrenia: a review. *J Psychiatr Pract*. 2004;10(1):5-16. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1097/00131746-200401000-00002>
52. TARRIER N. Cognitive behaviour therapy for schizophrenia—a review of development, evidence and implementation. *Psychotherapy and Psychosomatics*. 2005;74(3):136-44.
53. Jankovic J. Parkinson's disease: clinical features and diagnosis. *Journal of neurology, neurosurgery & psychiatry*. 2008;79(4):368-76.
54. Chi CT. fMRI research of characteristics of brain resting-state networks in patients with Parkinson's disease and intervention evaluation. <https://trialsearchwhooint/Trial2.aspx?TrialID=ChiCTR-TRC-09000507>. 2009.
55. Ravina B, Camicioli R, Como PG, Marsh L, Jankovic J, Weintraub D, et al. The impact of depressive symptoms in early Parkinson disease. *Neurology*. 2007;69(4):342-7. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1212/01.wnl.0000268695.63392.10>
56. Pohar SL, Allyson Jones C. The burden of Parkinson disease (PD) and concomitant comorbidities. *Arch Gerontol Geriatr*. 2009;49(2):317-21. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.archger.2008.11.006>
57. Chaudhuri KR, Healy DG, Schapira AH, National Institute for Clinical E. Non-motor symptoms of Parkinson's disease: diagnosis and management. *Lancet Neurol*. 2006;5(3):235-45. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(06\)70373-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(06)70373-8)
58. de Rijk MC, Launer LJ, Berger K, Breteler MM, Dartigues JF, Baldereschi M, et al. Prevalence of Parkinson's disease in Europe: A collaborative study of population-based cohorts. Neurologic Diseases in the Elderly Research Group. *Neurology*. 2000;54(11 Suppl 5):S21-3.
59. Hoy SM. Levodopa/carbidopa enteral suspension: a review in advanced Parkinson's disease. *Drugs*. 2019;79(15):1709-18. doi:
60. Poewe W, Seppi K, Tanner CM, Halliday GM, Brundin P, Volkman J, et al. Parkinson disease. *Nat Rev Dis Primers*. 2017;3:17013. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrdp.2017.13>
61. Kessler RC, Chiu WT, Demler O, Merikangas KR, Walters EE. Prevalence, severity, and comorbidity of 12-month DSM-IV disorders in the National Comorbidity Survey Replication. *Arch Gen Psychiatry*. 2005;62(6):617-27. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1001/archpsyc.62.6.617>
62. Rodrigues JM, Mestre M, Fredes LI. Qigong in the treatment of children with autism spectrum disorder: A systematic review. *J Integr Med*. 2019;17(4):250-60. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joim.2019.04.003>

63. Ma K-W. Acupuncture: its place in the history of Chinese medicine. *Acupuncture in Medicine*. 2000;18(2):88-99.
64. Pan SY, Litscher G, Gao SH, Zhou SF, Yu ZL, Chen HQ, et al. Historical perspective of traditional indigenous medical practices: the current renaissance and conservation of herbal resources. *Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine : eCAM*. 2014;2014:525340. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/525340>
65. Matos LC, Machado JP, Monteiro FJ, Greten HJ. Understanding Traditional Chinese Medicine Therapeutics: An Overview of the Basics and Clinical Applications. *Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland)*. 2021;9(3). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9030257>
66. Hu B, An H-M, Wang S-S, Chen J-J, Xu L. Preventive and Therapeutic Effects of Chinese Herbal Compounds against Hepatocellular Carcinoma. *Molecules [Internet]*. 2016; 21(2). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules21020142>
67. Gasmi A, Tippairote T, Mujawdiya PK, Menzel A, Lysiuk R, Shanaida M, et al. Traditional Chinese Medicine as the Preventive and Therapeutic Remedy for COVID-19. *Curr Med Chem*. 2024;31(21):3118-31. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2174/0929867330666230331084126>
68. Zou Q, Chen Y, Qin H, Tang R, Han T, Guo Z, et al. The role and mechanism of TCM in the prevention and treatment of infectious diseases. *Front Microbiol*. 2023;14:1286364. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2023.1286364>
69. Bernardo PS, Rodrigues JM. Acupuncture in acute COVID-19 treatment: A review of clinical evidence. *Revista Internacional de Acupuntura*. 2024;18(2):100298. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acu.2024.100298>
70. Rodrigues JM, Santos C, Ventura C, Machado J. Mental Health Benefits of a Traditional Vegetative Biofeedback Therapy Online Program during the COVID-19 Lockdown: A Controlled Trial. *Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland)*. 2022;10(10). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare10101843>
71. Porkert M. *The Theoretical Foundations of Chinese Medicine: Systems of Correspondence*: MIT Press; 1979.
72. Unschuld PU. *Medicine in China: A History of Ideas*: University of California Press; 2010. 9780520266131.
73. Veith I. *Huang Di Nei Jing Su Wen: The Yellow Emperor's Classic of Internal Medicine*: University of California Press; 1966.
74. Ni M. *The Yellow Emperor's Classic of Medicine: A New Translation of the Neijing Suwen with Commentary*: Shambhala; 1995. 9781570620805.
75. Moy GG, Han F. *History of Food Safety and Related Sciences: History of Foodborne Disease in Asia – Examples from China, India, and Japan*. In: Motarjemi Y, editor. *Encyclopedia of Food Safety*. Waltham: Academic Press; 2014. p. 22-7. 9780123786135.
76. Jiuzhang M, Lei G. *A General Introduction to Traditional Chinese Medicine*: Taylor & Francis; 2009. 9781040181232.
77. Dao Z. *From Xia Dynasty to Qing Dynasty: An Overview of the History of Chinese Dynasties*: DeepLogic.
78. Shi L. *The Religious History in Sui, Tang and Five Dynasties*: DeepLogic.
79. Helms JM. *Acupuncture Energetics: A Clinical Approach for Physicians*: Medical Acupuncture Publishers; 1995. 9781572507067.
80. Lu Y, Lui C. *Concepts and Theories of Traditional Chinese Medicine*: Science Press; 1998. 9787030056733.
81. Zhaoguo L, Qing W, Yurui X. *Key Concepts in Traditional Chinese Medicine*: Springer Nature Singapore; 2019. 9789811391361.
82. Rodrigues JM, Santos C, Ribeiro V, Silva A, Lopes L, Machado JP. Mental health benefits of traditional Chinese medicine – An umbrella review of meta-analyses. *Brain Behavior and Immunity Integrative*. 2023;2:100013. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbii.2023.100013>
83. Cheung T. The difference and similarity between traditional chinese and western medicine. *Chin J Integr Tradit West Med*. 2000(1):68-70.
84. Rodrigues JM, Lopes L, Gonçalves M, Machado JP. Taijiquan and qigong as a mindfulness cognitive-behavioural based therapy on the treatment of cothymia in school-age children - A preliminary study. *J Bodyw Mov Ther*. 2021;26:329-38. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbmt.2020.12.024>
85. Rodrigues JM, Lopes LT, Goncalves M, Machado JP. Perceived Health Benefits of Taijiquan and Qigong. *Altern Ther Health Med*. 2023;29(7):222-31.
86. Matos LC, Machado JP, Monteiro FJ, Greten HJ. Can Traditional Chinese Medicine Diagnosis Be Parameterized and Standardized? A Narrative Review. *Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland)*. 2021;9(2):177. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9020177>

87. Wang WY, Xie Y, Zhou H, Liu L. Contribution of traditional Chinese medicine to the treatment of COVID-19. *Phytomedicine : international journal of phytotherapy and phytopharmacology*. 2021;85:153279. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2020.153279>
88. Yang Y, Islam MS, Wang J, Li Y, Chen X. Traditional Chinese Medicine in the Treatment of Patients Infected with 2019-New Coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2): A Review and Perspective. *Int J Biol Sci*. 2020;16(10):1708-17. doi: <https://doi.org/10.7150/ijbs.45538>
89. Ho LTF, Chan KKH, Chung VCH, Leung TH. Highlights of traditional Chinese medicine frontline expert advice in the China national guideline for COVID-19. *Eur J Integr Med*. 2020;36:101116. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eujim.2020.101116>
90. World Health Organization. WHO international standard terminologies on traditional Chinese medicine, Geneva. 2022.
91. Bodeker G, Organization WH, Ong CK. WHO Global Atlas of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicine: WHO Centre for Health Development; 2005. 9789241562867.
92. Legal Status of Traditional Medicine and Complementary/Alternative Medicine: A Worldwide Review, I (2001).
93. World Health Organization. Traditional, complementary and integrative medicine [Available from: <http://www.who.int/traditional-complementary-integrative-medicine/en/>].
94. Thirthalli J, Zhou L, Kumar K, Gao J, Vaid H, Liu H, et al. Traditional, complementary, and alternative medicine approaches to mental health care and psychological wellbeing in India and China. *Lancet Psychiatry*. 2016;3(7):660-72. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(16\)30025-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(16)30025-6)
95. Portella CFS, Ghelman R, Abdala CVM, Schweitzer MC. Evidence map on the contributions of traditional, complementary and integrative medicines for health care in times of COVID-19. *Integr Med Res*. 2020;9(3):100473. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imr.2020.100473>
96. Mamtani R, Cimino A. A primer of complementary and alternative medicine and its relevance in the treatment of mental health problems. *Psychiatr Q*. 2002;73(4):367-81. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1020472218839>
97. Lake JH, Spiegel D. *Complementary and Alternative Treatments in Mental Health Care*: American Psychiatric Publishing; 2007. 9781585626397.
98. Carvalho JLDs, Nóbrega MdPSdS. Complementary therapies as resources for mental health in Primary Health Care. *Revista Gaúcha de Enfermagem*. 2018;38.
99. Soares Bernardo P. Traditional Chinese Medicine and Depression: A Bridge Between Eastern and Western Theories. *Journal of complementary therapies in health*. 2024;2(2). doi: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13623562>
100. Ferreira CdS, Luz MT. Shen: categoria estruturante da racionalidade médica chinesa. *História, Ciências, Saúde-Manguinhos*. 2007;14.
101. Greten HJ. Understanding TCM: Scientific Chinese medicine – The Heidelberg model. Preliminary, unrevised course version ed2008.
102. Santos RV, Rodrigues JM, Jesus MI. Review on the effects of obesity treatment with acupuncture and phytoacupuncture. *World Journal of Acupuncture - Moxibustion*. 2020;30(3):223-8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wjam.2020.07.002>
103. Isenburg K, Mawla I, Lee J, Gerber J, Kim J, Kim H, et al. Abstracts from Society for Acupuncture Research Acupuncture Research, Health Care Policy, & Community Health...Closing the Loop June 27–29, 2019 Burlington, VT. *The Journal of Alternative and Complementary Medicine*. 2019;25(10):A1-A37. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1089/acm.2019.29074.abstracts>
104. Smith CA, Collins CT, Levett KM, Armour M, Dahlen HG, Tan AL, et al. Acupuncture or acupressure for pain management during labour. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2020;2(2):CD009232. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD009232.pub2>
105. Yu S, Ortiz A, Gollub RL, Wilson G, Gerber J, Park J, et al. Acupuncture Treatment Modulates the Connectivity of Key Regions of the Descending Pain Modulation and Reward Systems in Patients with Chronic Low Back Pain. *J Clin Med*. 2020;9(6). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm9061719>

106. Shi Y, Yao S, Shen Z, She L, Xu Y, Liu B, et al. Effect of Electroacupuncture on Pain Perception and Pain-Related Affection: Dissociation or Interaction Based on the Anterior Cingulate Cortex and S1. *Neural Plast.* 2020;2020:8865096. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8865096>
107. Amorim D, Amado J, Brito I, Fiuza SM, Amorim N, Costeira C, et al. Acupuncture and electroacupuncture for anxiety disorders: A systematic review of the clinical research. *Complement Ther Clin Pract.* 2018;31:31-7. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctcp.2018.01.008>
108. Rodrigues JM, Simões K, Moreira O, Cruz G, Soares PB, Machado JP. Auricle reflex system: A practical approach to diagnosis and treatment. *Revista Internacional de Acupuntura.* 2024;18(1):100287. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acu.2024.100287>
109. Rodrigues JM, Ventura C, Abreu M, Santos C, Monte J, Machado JP, et al. Electro-Acupuncture Effects Measured by Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging—A Systematic Review of Randomized Clinical Trials. *Healthcare.* 2023;12(1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare12010002>
110. Silva H, Santos A, Monteiro A, Sousa IR, Rodrigues JM. Acupuncture for the Management of Breast Cancer: A Review of its Efficacy and Mechanisms. *Revista Internacional de Acupuntura.* 2024.
111. Wang H, Qi H, Wang B-s, Cui Y-y, Zhu L, Rong Z-x, et al. Is acupuncture beneficial in depression: a meta-analysis of 8 randomized controlled trials? *Journal of affective disorders.* 2008;111(2-3):125-34.
112. Smith CA, Armour M, Lee MS, Wang LQ, Hay PJ. Acupuncture for depression. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2018;3(3):CD004046. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD004046.pub4>
113. Shen X, Xia J, Adams CE. Acupuncture for schizophrenia. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews.* 2014(10).
114. Liu H, Chen L, Zhang Z, Geng G, Chen W, Dong H, et al. Effectiveness and safety of acupuncture combined with madopar for parkinson—s disease: a systematic review with meta-analysis. *Acupuncture in Medicine.* 2017;35(6):404-12.
115. Kim H, Kim HK, Kim SY, Kim YI, Yoo HR, Jung IC. Cognitive improvement effects of electro-acupuncture for the treatment of MCI compared with Western medications: a systematic review and Meta-analysis. *BMC complementary and alternative medicine.* 2019;19(1):13. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-018-2407-2>
116. Kim SH, Jeong JH, Lim JH, Kim BK. Acupuncture using pattern-identification for the treatment of insomnia disorder: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Integr Med Res.* 2019;8(3):216-26. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imr.2019.08.002>
117. Yang NN, Lin LL, Li YJ, Li HP, Cao Y, Tan CX, et al. Potential Mechanisms and Clinical Effectiveness of Acupuncture in Depression. *Curr Neuropharmacol.* 2022;20(4):738-50. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2174/1570159X19666210609162809>
118. Sun B, Cao X, Xin M, Guan R. Treatment of Depression with Acupuncture Based on Pathophysiological Mechanism. *Int J Gen Med.* 2024;17:347-57. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJGM.S448031>
119. Tu CH, MacDonald I, Chen YH. The Effects of Acupuncture on Glutamatergic Neurotransmission in Depression, Anxiety, Schizophrenia, and Alzheimer's Disease: A Review of the Literature. *Front Psychiatry.* 2019;10:14. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2019.00014>
120. Zhao Y, Zhang Z, Qin S, Fan W, Li W, Liu J, et al. Acupuncture for Parkinson's Disease: Efficacy Evaluation and Mechanisms in the Dopaminergic Neural Circuit. *Neural Plast.* 2021;2021:9926445. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/9926445>
121. Jia B, Li Z, Shi Y, Fei Y, Zhang H, Tu Y. Effect of electroacupuncture on changes of behavior and some related hormones of hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal axis in chronic stress model rats. *Acupuncture Research.* 2004;29(4):252-6.
122. Xiao X, Wei J, Li W, Ceng X, Shen X, Leng J, et al. Mechanism analysis of the antidepressant effect of acupuncture by regulating the HPA axis. *Shanghai Journal of Acupuncture and Moxibustion.* 2016:758-60.
123. Rodrigues JM, Matos LC, Francisco N, Dias A, Azevedo J, Machado J. Assessment of Qigong Effects on Anxiety of High-school Students: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Adv Mind Body Med.* 2021;35(3):10-9.
124. Howes SG. Can an online Tai Chi Qigong intervention reduce anxiety and promote self-actualisation in students with ADHD during lockdown? : University of Birmingham; 2021.

125. Wang F, Lee EK, Wu T, Benson H, Fricchione G, Wang W, et al. The effects of tai chi on depression, anxiety, and psychological well-being: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int J Behav Med*. 2014;21(4):605-17. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12529-013-9351-9>
126. Guo L, Kong Z, Zhang Y. Qigong-Based Therapy for Treating Adults with Major Depressive Disorder: A Meta-Analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2019;16(5):826. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16050826>
127. Chang PS, Knobf T, Oh B, Funk M. Physical and Psychological Health Outcomes of Qigong Exercise in Older Adults: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Am J Chin Med*. 2019;47(2):301-22. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0192415X19500149>
128. Lin R, Cui S, Yang J, Yang H, Feng Z, Wahner-Roedler DL, et al. Effects of Tai Chi on Patients with Mild Cognitive Impairment: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials. *Biomed Res Int*. 2021;2021:5530149. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/5530149>
129. Yang J, Zhang L, Tang Q, Wang F, Li Y, Peng H, et al. Tai Chi is Effective in Delaying Cognitive Decline in Older Adults with Mild Cognitive Impairment: Evidence from a Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine : eCAM*. 2020;2020:3620534. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/3620534>
130. Wu YH, He WB, Gao YY, Han XM. Effects of traditional Chinese exercises and general aerobic exercises on older adults with sleep disorders: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Integr Med*. 2021;19(6):493-502. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joim.2021.09.007>
131. Rodrigues JM, Santos C, Ribeiro V, Alvarenga A, Santos RV. Chinese Phytopharmacology in dermatology - A Systematic Review. *Pharmacological Research - Modern Chinese Medicine*. 2023;7:100255. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prmcm.2023.100255>
132. Aguiar R, Gehlen S, Oliveira R, Rodrigues JM. Recent advances in Chinese phytopharmacology for female infertility: A systematic review of high-quality randomized controlled trials. *Pharmacological Research - Modern Chinese Medicine*. 2024;13:100539. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prmcm.2024.100539>
133. Silva R, Lima da Fonseca M. Medicinal Mushrooms in Mental Health: A Review of TCM and Naturopathy. 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13353840>
134. Xiang YZ, Shang HC, Gao XM, Zhang BL. A comparison of the ancient use of ginseng in traditional Chinese medicine with modern pharmacological experiments and clinical trials. *Phytotherapy research : PTR*. 2008;22(7):851-8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ptr.2384>
135. Wei WL, Zeng R, Gu CM, Qu Y, Huang LF. *Angelica sinensis* in China-A review of botanical profile, ethnopharmacology, phytochemistry and chemical analysis. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*. 2016;190:116-41. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2016.05.023>
136. Li N, Zhou T, Wu F, Wang R, Zhao Q, Zhang JQ, et al. Pharmacokinetic mechanisms underlying the detoxification effect of *Glycyrrhizae Radix et Rhizoma* (Gancao): drug metabolizing enzymes, transporters, and beyond. *Expert Opin Drug Metab Toxicol*. 2019;15(2):167-77. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17425255.2019.1563595>
137. Gao Q, Shen L, Jiang B, Luan YF, Lin LN, Meng FC, et al. *Salvia miltiorrhiza*-Containing Chinese Herbal Medicine Combined With GnRH Agonist for Postoperative Treatment of Endometriosis: A Systematic Review and meta-Analysis. *Frontiers in pharmacology*. 2022;13:831850. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2022.831850>
138. Ried K. Chinese herbal medicine for female infertility: an updated meta-analysis. *Complement Ther Med*. 2015;23(1):116-28. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctim.2014.12.004>
139. Yang S, Xu Y, Peng W, Han D, Feng F, Wang Z, et al. Chinese herbal medicine for symptoms of depression and anxiety in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Complement Ther Clin Pract*. 2021;45:101470. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctcp.2021.101470>
140. Ho VW, Tan HY, Guo W, Li S, Wang N, Meng W, et al. Efficacy and Safety of Chinese Herbal Medicine on Treatment of Breast Cancer: A Meta-analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials. *Am J Chin Med*. 2021;49(7):1557-75. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0192415X21500737>

141. Zhang XW, Liu W, Jiang HL, Mao B. Chinese Herbal Medicine for Advanced Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Am J Chin Med.* 2018;46(5):923-52. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0192415X18500490>
142. Wang Y, Shi YH, Xu Z, Fu H, Zeng H, Zheng GQ. Efficacy and safety of Chinese herbal medicine for depression: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *J Psychiatr Res.* 2019;117:74-91. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2019.07.003>
143. Wang J, Liu J, Ni X, Nie G, Zeng Y, Cao X, et al. Adjuvant Therapy of Oral Chinese Herbal Medicine for Menopausal Depression: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine : eCAM.* 2018;2018:7420394. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/7420394>
144. Sun Y, Xu X, Zhang J, Chen Y. Treatment of depression with Chai Hu Shu Gan San: a systematic review and meta-analysis of 42 randomized controlled trials. *BMC complementary and alternative medicine.* 2018;18(1):66. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-018-2130-z>
145. Yang L, Shergis JL, Di YM, Zhang AL, Lu C, Guo X, et al. Managing Depression with Bupleurum chinense Herbal Formula: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials. *J Altern Complement Med.* 2020;26(1):8-24. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1089/acm.2019.0105>
146. Deng H, Xu J. Wendan decoction (Traditional Chinese medicine) for schizophrenia. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2017;6(6):CD012217. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD012217.pub2>
147. Fan X, Su Z, Nie S, Yang J, Zhang X, Tan D, et al. Efficacy and safety of Chinese herbal medicine Long Dan Xie Gan Tang in insomnia: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2020;99(11):e19410. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000019410>
148. Wang C, Yang Y, Ding X, Li J, Zhou X, Teng J, et al. Efficacy and safety of Shumian capsules in treating insomnia: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2021;100(50):e28194. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000028194>